

1 **Formation of Iron-Helium Alloys under High Pressure**

2
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11 12 **Key Points:**

- 13 • We examined the reaction between Fe and He to 42 GPa/2210 K and observed
14 fcc and distorted hcp phases with expanded volumes.
- 15 • Such expanded volumes suggest helium incorporation into interstitial sites
16 around the Fe atoms, with the He contents up to FeHe_{0.39}.
- 17 • Upon complete pressure release, these fcc and distorted hcp phases were still
18 observed while they largely lost helium from the Fe lattice.

19 20 **Abstract**

21 While helium is one of the noble gas elements characterized by their chemical inertness
22 at ambient conditions, recent experiments and calculations demonstrated that a small
23 amount of helium is included in molten iron under high pressures. Here we examined the
24 reaction between iron and helium to 42 GPa/2210 K and 20 GPa/>2300 K and found
25 remarkable volume expansion of the Fe lattice, which can be attributed to the
26 incorporation of helium. The helium contents, x in FeHe _{x} were estimated to be up to 0.12
27 for the fcc phase and 0.39 for the coexisting distorted hcp phase based on the present first-
28 principles calculations. Upon pressure release under room temperature, both of fcc and
29 distorted hcp were still present containing much lesser amounts of helium while partially
30 transforming into the bcc phase. These results support that the Earth's core can be a large
31 reservoir of primordial helium.

32 33 **Plain Language Summary**

34 It has been conventionally believed that high ³He/⁴He ratios (the ratio between primordial
35 ³He and ⁴He that can be produced by radioactive decay) observed in ocean island basalts

36 (OIBs) indicate the presence of undegassed primitive materials in the deep mantle.
37 Nevertheless, the recent finding that a certain amount of helium is incorporated into
38 molten iron from silicate implies that such high $^3\text{He}/^4\text{He}$ ratios are the consequence of the
39 supply of primordial ^3He from the core. In this study, we explored the reaction of helium
40 with iron at high pressure and temperature by monitoring the structure and volume of iron
41 based on synchrotron X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements. The results show the
42 remarkable expansion of the Fe lattice with respect to those of face-centered cubic (fcc)
43 and hexagonal-closed packed (hcp) pure Fe, suggesting the incorporation of helium. We
44 also observed that the reaction between iron and helium was kinetically hindered at
45 relatively low temperatures but promoted once a part of iron sample became molten. After
46 pressure was fully released, fcc and hcp FeHe_x exhibited significant losses of helium. It
47 might have led the underestimation of the metal/silicate partition coefficient of helium
48 obtained on samples recovered from high pressures.

49

50 **1. Introduction**

51 Recent experimental (Bouhifd et al., 2013; Roth et al., 2019) and theoretical studies
52 (Xiong et al., 2021; Yuan & Steinle-Neumann, 2021; Wang et al., 2022; Li et al., 2022)
53 of metal-silicate partitioning of helium under high pressure and temperature (P - T) suggest
54 that helium could be incorporated from silicate melt to molten iron in a magma ocean and
55 the Earth's core is an important reservoir of primordial ^3He . Its transfer from the core to
56 the mantle might be responsible for the observed high $^3\text{He}/^4\text{He}$ ratios (Horton et al., 2023),
57 instead of undegassed materials in the deep mantle that could have been once molten
58 during Earth's accretion (Porcelli & Halliday, 2001; Ferrick & Korenaga, 2023; Deng &
59 Du, 2023). In addition to helium, the presence of xenon, another noble gas element, in
60 the core was also suggested to explain the "missing" Xe problem (e.g., Marty, 2012).

61 Both theory and experiments have revealed that noble gases are no longer inert elements
62 under high pressures, forming a variety of compounds including those with noble gas
63 insertion, in particular for heavy noble gases [see reviews by Miao (2020) and Sanloup
64 (2020)]. Xenon has been shown to react with iron under high pressures, indicating that
65 pressure changes its electronegativity and reactivity (Stavrou et al., 2018). The
66 calculations by Lee & Steinle-Neumann (2006) showed that hcp Fe incorporates a small
67 amount of Xe under Earth's core pressures. Furthermore, the formation of Fe_3Xe was
68 predicted (Zhu et al., 2014) and experimentally confirmed above 200 GPa and 2000 K
69 (Stavrou et al., 2018). In addition, xenon-iron oxides were found to exist above 150 GPa
70 by theory (Peng et al., 2020), and the incorporation of xenon into SiO_2 was observed by

71 experiments at pressures as low as ~ 1 GPa (Sanloup et al., 2002; Crépinson et al., 2019).
72 On the other hand, helium compounds are little known. Theory has predicted the
73 existence of Na_2HeO and Na_2He above 15 and 113 GPa, respectively (Dong et al., 2017).
74 FeO_2He and $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{He}$ were also calculated to be stable respectively at >120 GPa (Zhang
75 et al., 2018) and >296 GPa (Liu et al., 2015). The reaction of helium with iron has been
76 investigated under high P - T through studies of the partitioning of helium between liquid
77 iron and molten silicate as mentioned above. The computational simulations by Yuan &
78 Steinle-Neumann (2021) found that helium atoms coalesced into a cluster in liquid iron,
79 suggesting its low solubility. To our knowledge, the formation of solid iron-helium alloy
80 (or insertion of He atoms into the Fe lattice) has not been experimentally explored at high
81 pressures, while the theoretical work by Monserrat et al. (2018) predicted iron-helium
82 compounds at the terapascal pressure range.

83 Here we experimentally examined the reaction between iron and helium at high P - T in a
84 laser-heated diamond-anvil cell (DAC), into which an iron foil and helium gas were
85 loaded. Upon heating to temperatures likely above the melting temperature in the Fe-He
86 system at 20–42 GPa, we observed the appearance of the fcc phase whose unit-cell
87 volumes were remarkably larger than those of pure Fe at equivalent pressure. We also
88 found in the second run that the volumes of the fcc and coexisting distorted hcp phases
89 were substantially expanded. Such large volumes are most likely the consequence of the
90 incorporation of helium atoms into the interstitial sites in the fcc and distorted hcp lattices
91 of iron and the formation of FeHe_x alloys ($x = 0.08$ to 0.39). When pressure was released,
92 these fcc and hcp Fe largely lost helium but were still present without fully transforming
93 into the body-centered cubic (bcc) structure.

94 **2. Experimental and Computational Methods**

95 High P - T experiments were performed by using laser-heated DAC techniques. We used
96 diamond anvils with 300 μm culet size. Their surface was coated with a thin layer of TiO_2
97 by sputtering in run #1 in order to prevent possible migration of helium into the diamonds
98 (Ohta et al., 2015). A rhenium gasket was preindented to 35–37 μm thickness. After a ~ 10
99 μm thick pure Fe foil ($>99.999\%$ purity, Toho Zinc) was put into a sample chamber,
100 supercritical helium was loaded under 200 MPa by using a high-pressure gas apparatus
101 (PRETECH Co., Ltd) at SPring-8. A high-pressure vessel and a gas line were vacuumed
102 for 10 min and then purged by helium gas before loading into the DAC. In run #2, the
103 <10 μm thick Al_2O_3 plates were also employed for thermal insulation, while large space
104 was left for helium (Figure S1 in Supporting Information). The XRD patterns collected

105 before and after heating at high pressures showed the peaks from hcp solid helium in both
106 runs (Figures 1, 2).

107 After compression to a pressure of interest at room temperature, the iron foil was heated
108 from both sides with a couple of 100 W single-mode Yb fiber lasers at the beamline
109 BL10XU, SPring-8. The laser beam was converted to one with a flat energy distribution
110 by beam-shaping optics, and the laser-heated spot was $\sim 20\text{--}30\ \mu\text{m}$ across. The one-
111 dimensional temperature distribution across a laser-heated spot was obtained by a
112 spectro-radiometric method (Hirao et al., 2020). Synchrotron XRD patterns of the sample
113 were collected on a flat panel X-ray detector (Varex Imaging, XRD1611CP3)
114 before/during/after laser heating under high pressure. The incident X-ray beam was
115 monochromatized to a wavelength of $0.41298\text{--}0.41429\ \text{\AA}$ ($\sim 30\ \text{keV}$) and focused to $6\ \mu\text{m}$
116 in diameter. The sample temperature is the average of those over $6\ \mu\text{m}$ area at a hot spot,
117 from which XRD data were obtained. Pressure was primarily determined at 300 K from
118 the unit-cell volume of solid helium (Loubeyre et al., 1993), which is consistent with
119 those estimated based on the Raman shift of a diamond anvil (Akahama & Kawamura,
120 2004) and from the unit-cell volume of Al_2O_3 and its equation of state (Dewaele &
121 Torrent, 2013) (Table 1). Since the XRD peaks of helium were not clear during
122 decompression in run #2, we employed the pressure from Al_2O_3 at 11.6 GPa. We
123 estimated pressures at high temperatures by adding the contributions of thermal pressure,
124 5% pressure increase with each temperature increase of 1000 K (Fiquet et al., 2010;
125 Hirose et al., 2019), to those measured at room temperature after heating.

126 We recovered a sample from run #1 and examined possible contamination to iron by
127 carbon, oxygen, rhenium, and tungsten on its cross section (Figure S2 and Table S1 in
128 Supporting Information). The sample cross section at the laser-heated portion was
129 prepared parallel to the compression axis using a focused Ga ion beam (dual beam FIB)
130 (Thermoscientific, Helios 5 UC). The scanning ion microscope (SIM) image was
131 obtained with an accelerating voltage of 30 kV. The Fe, C, O, Re, and W contents in the
132 Fe sample were quantified by a field emission-type electron probe micro analyzer, FE-
133 EPMA (JEOL, JXA-8530F) with an acceleration voltage of 12 kV and a beam current of
134 15 nA. We used LIF (Fe, W), LDE2H (C), LDE1 (O), and PETH (Re) as analyzing
135 crystals. Carbon concentration was quantified based on a calibration line obtained by a
136 carbon-free copper mesh, Fe-0.84 wt%C (JSS066-6, the Japan Iron and Steel Federation),
137 and Fe_3C (Sakai et al., 2022). Fe, W, Al_2O_3 , and Re were also used as standards.

138 We estimated the amounts of helium x in FeHe_x with expanded volumes by considering
139 that helium, similar to hydrogen, is incorporated not substitutionally but interstitially

140 around Fe atoms. Indeed, the size of helium atom is small comparable to that of hydrogen,
141 and such interstitial incorporation is reasonable, causing remarkable volume expansion
142 of the fcc and hcp phases. The helium content x in FeHe_x was calculated from the lattice
143 volume of Fe observed at high pressure and ambient temperature;

$$144 \quad x = \frac{V_{\text{FeHe}_x} - V_{\text{Fe}}}{\Delta V_{\text{He}}}, \quad (1)$$

145 where V_{FeHe_x} and V_{Fe} are the volumes of FeHe_x and Fe per Fe atom, respectively, and ΔV_{He}
146 corresponds to an increase in V_{Fe} by incorporating a He atom. The reference V_{Fe} is from
147 Tsujino et al. (2013) and Dewaele et al. (2006) for the fcc and hcp phases, respectively.
148 The ΔV_{He} at high pressure is from the difference between the volumes of pure Fe and
149 stoichiometric FeHe, which were obtained by static first-principles calculations in this
150 study (see below). The hydrogen content in FeH_x has been estimated in a similar manner
151 (e.g., Thompson et al., 2018; Tagawa et al., 2021).

152 We performed first-principles calculations to obtain the volumes of fcc Fe and
153 stoichiometric FeHe in a pressure range from 0 to 50 GPa (Figure S3 and Table S2 in
154 Supporting Information) by using the projector-augmented wave (PAW) method, which
155 was implemented in the Quantum ESPRESSO package (Giannozzi et al., 2009). We used
156 a Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE)-type generalized gradient approximation (GGA) for
157 the exchange-correlation potential (Perdew et al., 1996). The kinetic energy cutoff for
158 wavefunctions was set to be 100 Ry. We adopted $7 \times 7 \times 7$ k-point grids. In stoichiometric
159 FeHe, we put He atoms on the octahedral interstitial sites similar to FeH (Gomi & Hirose,
160 2023). Structures were fully relaxed under pressure. Both nonmagnetic (NM) and
161 ferromagnetic (FM) states were examined. The ΔV_{He} obtained as a difference between the
162 volumes of pure Fe and stoichiometric FeHe per Fe atom is comparable to the volume of
163 solid He per He atom at high pressures greater than ~ 5 GPa, while the latter is
164 significantly larger below ~ 1 GPa (Loubeyre et al., 1993) (Figure S3). We employed the
165 ΔV_{He} from the calculations on Fe and FeHe for the NM and FM states at 12 GPa and
166 higher and at 1 bar, respectively, to estimate helium concentration in iron. In addition, we
167 assumed the ΔV_{He} for hcp (and distorted hcp as described below) to be identical with that
168 for fcc calculated here, which is supported by a previous study on ΔV_{H} (an increase in V_{Fe}
169 by incorporating a H atom) (Tagawa, Gomi, et al., 2022; Gomi & Hirose, 2023).

170 3. Experimental Results

171 We carried out two separate experiments to examine the reaction between iron and helium.

172 In run #1 with only Fe foil and He gas in a sample chamber of DAC before compression
173 (Table 1), the sample was first compressed to 43 GPa at room temperature. The XRD
174 pattern showed the coexistence of hcp Fe and solid hcp He (Figure 1a). Subsequently we
175 heated the sample by gradually increasing the laser power output. The fcc phase appeared
176 (Figure 1b) when the sample temperature reached 2140 K on average in the hottest 6 μm
177 area (2210 K at maximum) on one side and 1670 K on the other side—the identical laser
178 power output for both sides resulted in such temperature difference likely because of the
179 different thickness of the He layer loaded originally as gas. It is possible that a small
180 portion of the sample was molten at 2210 K since the melting temperature in the Fe-He
181 system should be lower than the melting point of pure Fe, ~ 2400 K at 42 GPa (Sinmyo et
182 al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2016). A large portion remained solid including the inside of the
183 sample that was below 1670 K (sample surface is the hottest during laser heating of a
184 metal sample). We kept the sample in this condition for 10 min and then quenched
185 temperature. The XRD pattern collected at 38 GPa and 300 K after quenching
186 demonstrated the fcc and hcp Fe phases along with hcp helium (Figure 1c). While the
187 unit-cell volume of the hcp phase was similar to that of pure Fe, that of the fcc phase was
188 larger by 3.6% at equivalent pressure (Figure 3). Considering such volume expansion was
189 caused by the incorporation of helium into the interstitial sites around Fe atoms, the
190 amount of helium is calculated to be $x = 0.081$ when using the ΔV_{He} obtained in the present
191 calculations (Figure S3).

192 This sample was recovered from a DAC at ambient condition and examined for possible
193 contamination by carbon (from diamond anvils), oxygen, rhenium (from gasket), and
194 tungsten (from a needle used for loading an iron foil). We performed the FE-EPMA
195 analyses of the relatively large Fe grains that should have been heated to high
196 temperatures (Figure S2) and found <0.42 wt% C, <0.28 wt% O, <0.17 wt% Re, and
197 <0.38 wt% W (Table S1). Such minimal contamination does not explain the large volume
198 expansion by 3.6%.

199 Run #2 was conducted using the Al_2O_3 pressure medium as a thermal insulator (Figures
200 S1a, b). After compression, we found XRD peaks from hcp Fe, Al_2O_3 , and solid He before
201 heating at 29 GPa (Figure 2a). New peaks did not appear during heating to <1300 K for
202 10 min. When we gradually increased the laser power output, the Fe sample slightly
203 moved likely due to extensive melting of He, and the edge of the Fe sample, which was
204 thin and thus sandwiched by thick thermal insulation layers, was suddenly heated to high
205 temperatures, likely >2300 K at the maximum. It is above the melting temperature of Fe
206 at this pressure (Zhang et al., 2016; Sinmyo et al., 2019), which should have caused this

207 part of the sample to melt. We then shut off the laser and collected the XRD pattern at the
208 position marked by plus (+) in [Figure S1b](#), showing the presence of the fcc and (distorted)
209 hcp Fe phases with expanded volumes. We re-increased the sample temperature at this
210 position to 1660 K (1620 K on the other side) in 10 min, kept that condition for another
211 5 min, and then quenched. Those fcc and (distorted) hcp phases remained in the XRD
212 patterns collected during and after heating ([Figures 2b, c](#)). The hcp phase exhibited peak
213 splitting, in particular of the 101 peak, possibly because of a slight crystallographic
214 distortion to an orthorhombic structure (Sikka, 2005). Both of these fcc and distorted hcp
215 phases, in particular the latter, exhibited the unit-cell volumes that are remarkably larger
216 than those of the corresponding pure Fe phases ([Figure 3, Table 1](#)). Their volumes
217 measured at 19 GPa and 300 K indicate $\text{FeHe}_{0.12}$ for fcc and $\text{FeHe}_{0.39}$ for distorted hcp.
218 The XRD patterns obtained from different areas of the sample showed that these fcc and
219 distorted hcp phases were widely distributed with identical unit-cell volumes
220 (homogeneous helium concentrations).

221 Subsequently this sample was decompressed, and the XRD patterns were collected at 12
222 GPa and 1 bar. We observed the fcc and distorted hcp FeHe_x phases at 12 GPa, whose
223 helium concentrations practically did not change by decompression from 19 GPa. Upon
224 complete pressure release, on the other hand, the bcc phase appeared, while both fcc and
225 distorted hcp phases were still present ([Figure 2d](#)). The volume of the bcc phase was
226 equivalent to that of bcc pure Fe, indicating the absence of helium in it. Those of fcc and
227 distorted hcp were still larger than those of the corresponding pure Fe phases;
228 nevertheless, the differences diminished compared to those at high pressures ([Figure 3](#)).
229 Employing ΔV_{He} for the FM state at 1 bar, helium concentrations in the fcc and distorted
230 hcp phases were found to be $x = 0.05$ and 0.19 , respectively, which are remarkably smaller
231 than those at 12 GPa and higher pressures ($x = 0.12$ and $0.37\text{--}0.39$). These indicate that
232 helium was largely lost, by more than half, from the Fe lattice upon complete pressure
233 release.

234 **4. Discussion**

235 **4.1. Incorporation of Helium into Solid Iron**

236 The expanded volumes of fcc and distorted hcp Fe described above are attributed to the
237 incorporation of helium. The FE-EPMA analyses on a cross section of a recovered sample
238 did not show any remarkable contamination by C, O, Re, and W from diamond nor gasket
239 ([Table S2](#) in Supporting Information). The reaction between iron and helium is likely to
240 be a kinetic process, and it occurred in this study when a part of the Fe sample became

241 molten in the Fe-He system. Indeed, in a separate run we did not report above, no XRD
242 peaks were observed from expanded Fe phases when the Fe + He sample was heated to
243 ~1700 K on both sides for 8 min at 40 GPa.

244 While fcc FeHe_{0.08} was the only helium-bearing phase in run #1, fcc FeHe_{0.12} coexisted
245 with helium-richer distorted hcp FeHe_{0.39} in run #2. The smaller He concentration in Fe
246 in the former run might have been due to the presence of a smaller amount of helium
247 around the laser-heated spot before heating. The result of run #2 suggests that there is a
248 miscibility gap between the He-poor fcc phase and the He-rich hcp phase, at least around
249 20 GPa. It contrasts the phase relations in the Fe-H system, where H-rich fcc coexists
250 with H-poor hcp above ~30 GPa (Tagawa, Helffrich, et al., 2022).

251 **4.2. Escape of Helium from Iron upon Pressure Release**

252 The present experiments demonstrate that both fcc and distorted hcp Fe-He were still
253 present after decompression down to 1 bar. Their unit-cell volumes were larger than those
254 of fcc and hcp pure Fe at ambient condition that are estimated by extrapolations of the
255 pressure-volume relations (Figure 3). Nevertheless, their helium concentrations at 1 bar
256 dropped to less than half from those found upon synthesis at 20 GPa and during
257 decompression to 12 GPa (Table 1). Indeed, the He-free bcc phase also appeared at 1 bar,
258 coexisting with these fcc and distorted hcp phases (Figure 2d). These indicate that a large
259 fraction of helium included in fcc and hcp iron escaped from the Fe lattice. It is in part
260 similar to but contrasts Fe-H alloys, which fully lose hydrogen when their crystal structure
261 changes from fcc/hcp to bcc (e.g., Iizuka-Oku et al., 2017; Tagawa et al., 2021).

262 **4.3. Possible Presence of Helium in Earth's Core**

263 These experiments show that a substantial amount of helium is incorporated into solid
264 iron, at least above 20 GPa and 1660 K under helium-saturated conditions. It may be
265 analogous to previous calculations and experiments on the xenon incorporation to hcp Fe
266 (Lee & Steinle-Neumann, 2006) and the formation of Fe₃Xe (Zhu et al., 2014; Stavrou et
267 al., 2018). Simply the present results stand for the presence of helium in planetary metallic
268 cores including the Earth's. A large fraction of primordial ³He could have been
269 sequestered into the core via metal-silicate chemical equilibrium in a deep magma ocean
270 under high *P-T* (e.g., Bouhifd et al., 2013; Roth et al., 2019; Li et al., 2022).

271 Indeed, our observation of the helium escape from iron suggests that the metal/silicate
272 partition coefficients and the possible helium content in the Earth's core might have been

273 underestimated by earlier reports based on the analyses of samples recovered from high-
274 pressure experiments (Bouhifd et al., 2013). The results of run #2 in this study
275 demonstrated that more than half of helium included in solid iron at high pressures
276 escaped upon complete pressure release. More could be lost under evacuated
277 environments since the escape of He atoms from the Fe lattice likely involves kinetics.
278 The previous DAC experiments by Bouhifd et al. (2013) reported the metal/silicate
279 partition coefficients of helium to be 10^{-3} to 10^{-2} , based on the mass spectrometry analyses
280 of helium in iron on recovered samples. They found strong helium enrichment near the
281 surface of the iron sample, which might be the consequence of the helium escape from
282 inside.

283 The present study supports the recent argument that the high $^3\text{He}/^4\text{He}$ ratios observed in
284 OIBs are attributed to the core as an important reservoir of primordial ^3He (e.g., Porcelli
285 & Halliday, 2001; Ferrick & Korenaga, 2023). The theoretically calculated very low
286 metal/silicate partition coefficient of neon might not reconcile the $^3\text{He}/^{22}\text{Ne}$ primordial
287 noble gas ratios found in OIBs with the core being their source (Li et al., 2022), but such
288 calculations are not consistent with experimental determinations (Bouhifd et al., 2020)
289 and await further verification.

290 **5. Conclusions**

291 We examined the reaction between iron and helium under high P - T and observed the
292 appearance of iron with expanded unit-cell volumes when a part of the iron sample
293 became molten, which is attributed to the incorporation of He into the interstitial sites
294 around Fe atoms. With ΔV_{He} (an increase in V_{Fe} by incorporating a He atom) theoretically
295 obtained in this study, helium concentrations in the expanded fcc and distorted-hcp phases
296 were calculated. Our data show that fcc $\text{FeHe}_{0.08}$ formed in run #1 and that fcc $\text{FeHe}_{0.12}$
297 and distorted hcp $\text{FeHe}_{0.39}$ coexisted in run #2. While these fcc and distorted hcp Fe-He
298 were still found, together with the He-free bcc phase, upon decompression to ambient
299 condition, they lost large fractions of helium from iron, similar to the case of iron-
300 hydrogen alloys. It suggests that previous studies on the metal/silicate partitioning of
301 helium might have underestimated the partition coefficients by analyzing samples
302 recovered from high-pressure experiments. The present results support the sequestration
303 of a large fraction of primordial ^3He into the Earth's core. We stand for the recent
304 argument that high $^3\text{He}/^4\text{He}$ ratios found in OIBs originate not from a hypothetical,
305 undegassed primitive mantle but from the metallic core (e.g., Bouhifd et al., 2013; Ferrick
306 & Korenaga, 2023).

307 **Data Availability Statement**

308 Datasets for this research are found in [Tables S1](#) and [S2](#) available online (from
309 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10164370>).

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Table 1
Experimental Results

Run #	Sample (+ medium)	P (GPa) by He	P (GPa) Raman/ Al_2O_3	T (K)	Observed phases	V (\AA^3) ^a	fcc ΔV (\AA^3) ^b	He content, x	V (\AA^3) ^a	hcp, distorted hcp ΔV (\AA^3) ^b	He content, x
1	Fe + He	41.5	44.5 ^c	2210–1670	fcc Fe-He, hcp Fe						
		37.9	40.6 ^c	300	fcc FeHe _{0.08} , hcp Fe, solid He	10.079(1)	0.347	0.081	9.539(51)	-0.075	-0.017
2	Fe + He (+ Al_2O_3)	20.4	22.6 ^d	>2300/1660	fcc Fe-He, distorted hcp Fe-He						
		18.5	20.5 ^d	300	fcc FeHe _{0.12} , distorted hcp FeHe _{0.39} , solid He	11.096(11)	0.645	0.120	12.295(19)	2.105	0.392
		n.d.	11.6 ^d	300	fcc FeHe _{0.12} , distorted hcp FeHe _{0.37}	11.503(18)	0.709	0.118	12.772(91)	2.198	0.367
		0.0		300	fcc FeHe _{0.05} , distorted hcp FeHe _{0.09} , bcc Fe	12.140(5)	0.608	0.046	13.735(65)	2.501	0.188

^aVolume per Fe atom. ^bVolume difference per Fe atom between observed and pure Fe reported by Tsujino et al. (2013) and Dewaele et al. (2006) for fcc and hcp phases, respectively. ^cMeasured by Raman for pressure at 300 K. ^dMeasured by Al_2O_3 .

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Figure 1. XRD patterns collected in run #1 (a) before, (b) during, and (c) after heating. The peaks from fcc FeHe_{0.08} appeared upon heating to the maximum 2210 K at 42 GPa, whose volume was remarkably larger than that of pure Fe [see triangles in (c) indicating the peak positions for pure fcc Fe]. See text for details.

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472 **Figure 2.** XRD patterns collected in run #2 (a) before, (b) during heating at 1660 K, and
 473 (c) after quenching temperature to 300 K at ~ 20 GPa and (d) upon decompression to 1
 474 bar. The peaks from fcc $\text{FeHe}_{0.12}$ and distorted hcp $\text{FeHe}_{0.39}$ were observed when the
 475 sample was once heated to >2300 K. Their volumes were substantially expanded with
 476 respect to those of corresponding fcc and hcp pure Fe [see black and blue triangles in (c)
 477 indicating the peak positions for fcc and hcp pure Fe, respectively]. Both fcc and distorted
 478 hcp lost their helium to a large extent upon decompression to 1 bar, while partly
 479 transforming into the helium-free bcc phase. See text for more details.

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484 **Figure 3.** The volumes per Fe atom of the observed fcc (runs #1 and #2) and distorted
 485 hcp phases (run #2) after quenching temperature to 300 K. Black, fcc; blue, (distorted)
 486 hcp. They are compared to those of fcc and hcp pure Fe (V_{Fe} , solid lines) previously
 487 determined by Tsujino et al. (2013) and Dewaele et al. (2006), respectively. The
 488 compression curves of FeHe_{0.5} for the non-magnetic (NM) (broken lines) and
 489 ferromagnetic (FM) (dotted lines) states are estimated from V_{Fe} (solid lines) by these
 490 earlier experiments and ΔV_{He} by the present static calculations of pure Fe and
 491 stoichiometric FeHe (see [Figure S3](#)).

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Geophysical Research Letters

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Supporting Information for

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Formation of Iron-Helium Alloys under High Pressure

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499

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Table S1*FE-EPMA Analyses of a Sample Recovered from Run #1*

Point # ^a	Fe	C	O	Re	W	Total
1	99.76	0.10	0.13	0.07	0.24	100.29
2	99.51	0.21	0.19	0.01	n.d.	99.92
3	97.88	0.17	0.17	0.05	n.d.	98.27
4	98.42	0.32	0.21	0.12	n.d.	99.06
5	99.63	0.28	0.21	0.07	n.d.	100.20
6	98.55	0.42	0.28	n.d.	0.38	99.62
7	99.70	0.02	0.12	0.06	0.07	99.97
8	99.42	0.01	0.12	0.01	n.d.	99.57
9	99.07	0.18	0.13	n.d.	n.d.	99.39
10	98.25	0.26	0.20	n.d.	n.d.	98.70
11	98.34	0.11	0.17	0.04	n.d.	98.66
12	99.43	0.15	0.15	n.d.	n.d.	99.73
13	100.52	0.06	0.05	n.d.	n.d.	100.63
14	98.85	0.07	0.07	0.03	n.d.	99.01
15	97.39	0.09	0.04	0.07	0.21	97.79
16	98.52	0.07	0.07	n.d.	n.d.	98.66
17	99.51	0.07	0.11	n.d.	n.d.	99.69
18	100.18	0.08	0.09	0.08	n.d.	100.42
19	97.82	0.07	0.01	n.d.	n.d.	97.90
20	100.07	0.10	0.06	0.05	n.d.	100.28
21	99.27	0.10	0.12	n.d.	n.d.	99.49
22	99.05	0.11	0.03	0.17	n.d.	99.36
23	98.72	0.14	0.14	0.01	0.14	99.14
24	98.83	0.08	0.07	n.d.	n.d.	98.98

^aSee Figure S2.

The C content tends to be higher for points analyzed later (the position # does not correspond to the sequence of analysis).

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Table S2*Parameters in Birch-Murnaghan Equations of State for fcc FeHe and Fe*

	FeHe (FM)	FeHe (NM)	Fe (FM)	Fe (NM)
V_0 (Å ³)	24.56(35)	18.25(2)	10.68(0)	10.35(0)
K_0 (GPa)	21.5(24)	61.6(8)	226(1)	285(1)
K'	4.8(2)	5.0(1)	4.7(1)	4.5(0)

P (GPa) = $1.5 K_0(x^{-7} - x^{-5})[1 + 0.75(K' - 4)(x^{-2} - 1)]$ where $x = (V/V_0)^{1/3}$, and K_0 and K' are isothermal bulk modulus and its pressure derivative, respectively, at ambient pressure.

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519 **Figure S1.** Photomicrographs of a sample chamber (a) before loading helium gas and (b)
520 after compression to 29 GPa in run #2. Plus (+) mark in (b) indicates the position at the
521 center of a laser-heated spot.

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526 **Figure S2.** Scanning ion microscope (SIM) image of a sample cross section at the center
527 of the laser-heated hot spot for run #1. Red circles and numbers indicate the points of FE-
528 EPMA analyses (see [Table S1](#)).

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533 **Figure S3.** First-principles calculations of the volumes per Fe atom for pure Fe (broken
534 lines) and stoichiometric FeHe (dotted lines). Black, non-magnetic (NM) state; red,
535 ferromagnetic (FM) state. Parameters in the third-order Birch Murnaghan equations of
536 state (EoSs) obtained from these data are listed in [Table S2](#). Orange solid curve shows the
537 volume of He per atom reported by earlier experiments on solid He (Loubeyre et al.,
538 1993). Black and red solid curves indicate ΔV_{He} (volume increase of Fe by incorporating
539 a He atom), which corresponds to the difference between the volumes of Fe and FeHe
540 given by their EoSs at each pressure.